

SMART TRANSCRIPT: A SECURED MODEL FOR TRANSCRIPT TRANSMISSION BASED ON DIGITAL SIGNATURE

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Abstract

Mobile communication has greatly reduced the burden and risk of travelling while raising increase of electronic transactions. And though a lot of web based system has been proposed for transcript processing, yet many institution have preferred the use of traditional postal services to perform the issuance, transfer and verification of transcript due the sensitive nature of transcript and the use of sophisticated software for editing and photo-editing of electronic documents. This research analyses and compared existing works and proposes a secured model for transcript transmission based on digital signature. Using our proposed system the stakeholders would need not to worry about the authenticity of these electronic transcripts since the digital signature will truly proof the identity of the issuer and hence, reduce the cost and inconvenience associated with traditional transcript processing.

Keyword: Transcript processing, Digital signature, Time-stamping Blockchain

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Transcript is the official document issued by an academic awarding institution to an admitting institution on the academic performance of a student. The entire process comprise of transcript application, transcript processing, transcript transmission and transcript verification. Firstly, the student will apply to his formal school and pay some processing fees. Then the exams and record unit of the school will process the request and forward the student's transcript to his new school. After receiving the transcript, the new school will write the registrar of the formal school to authenticate the transcript by confirming in writing that the transcript was actually sent by him (the registrar of the formal school).

Because of the delays usually encountered in transmission and the malicious tendencies of some student to tamper the transcript in favour of their admission, so many techniques have been proposed to facilitate the speedy processing of these paper transcript s as well as their security against unauthorized access and eventual tampering. These techniques include the use of postal agencies to send and track the transcript; the use of web-based system to apply for the transcript; and the use of specialized computer software to produce the transcript from existing databases. However, the verification of these transcripts have been left to traditional system of postal services, thereby giving room to additional delays, cost, human intervention and human error.

In this paper, we designed a secured model for transmitting of electronic transcripts based on the use of digital signature. The performance of our system will be measured on its ability to forward digitally signed transcripts; and authenticate these transcripts by verifying the signatures of the issuer.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Information-driven enterprises are extremely concerned with the security of digital documents. This is due to the ease with which digital documents can be edited in comparison to their paper counterparts because of the availability of word processors, optical character recognition (OCR), image editing, and other associated software. Time-stamping technology and digital signature and was developed as a result of the requirement to preserve the veracity of these digital documents and to offer proof that they be existent at a specific moment and on a specific date. The development of public and private sector confidence in electronic commerce and circuit boards depends heavily on digital signatures. (Lui-kwan, 1999).

The same way that handwritten signatures validate printed papers, digital signatures do the same for electronic documents. A public key and a private key are the two keys it employs. Since these keys are mathematically tied to one another, only the sender's public key can be used to decipher a message encrypted with a private key. While a public key is visible to everyone, a private key is only known to the sender. The document sender signs the genuine document with his private key and then sends the signed document to the intended recipient. The recipient of a signed document will check the document's integrity using the document owner's public key after receiving it.

A certificate authority (CA) issues the electronic identity cards that serve as the basis for digital signatures. These CAs are reputable third parties, including banks or businesses with a focus on digital signatures. Public key infrastructure (PKI) is a collection of tools, procedures, and policies of an organization that facilitate the use of public key cryptography to confirm the veracity of public keys, provides the foundation for digital signatures (Chaudhary, Sam & Gandihinagar, 2017; Haung, Chen & Qu, 2009).

Haung, Chen, and Qu (2009) presented an improved digital signature technique based on stamps (or digital signatures) in an effort to stop the unauthorized alteration of digital data

and the use of identity theft to commit cybercrimes. The suggested method would make it possible to verify that digital content (messages) was transmitted by the signer and was not altered in transit.

Reddy, Bhat, Chetwani, and Reddy (2011) suggested employing PKI technology (or a digital signature) to share documents in a private network in a secure manner. The authors utilized Java and JSP programs to show how to check a document's digital signature in a private network. In its implementation, a closed (private) network's participants were trusted thanks to a private CA. The researchers used p12 files to transport the private keys securely while signing and verifying digitally signed documents at the centralized server and guaranteeing the private key hadn't been compromised in transit.

The use of an RSA digital signature for the transfer of signed documents between government entities was proposed by Barik and Karforma (2012). Their system used RSA to sign (encrypt) and design (decrypt) the message digest. Its hash method was MD5 (Message Digest 5). The author listed a few uses for digital signatures, including filling out income tax forms, banking services, passport and visa information, voter identification, checking the status of national citizen cards, insurance, and risk management.

The progress of internet business and electronic commerce is meant to be influenced by the few bills on electronic commerce that have been researched by Lui-kwan (1999). Lui-kwan showed that there is a growing interest in online commerce and the necessity for regulation by using data from a number of surveys from well-known internet polls. When conversing online, parties will be able to validate their documents thanks to digital signatures, which allow businesses to confirm their real identities.

A document's integrity is maintained and its existence at the time of the time stamping is guaranteed by time stamping. A time-stamped electronic document cannot be changed

without being noticed. By ensuring that a digital signature can be successfully verified upon the expiration or cancelation (if any) of the certificate that was used to sign the document, time stamps improve digital signatures. The same way that CAs issue digital certificates needed for digital signing, Time Stamping Authorities (TSAs) also issue time stamps. Each time stamp has a unique time-stamp serial number as well as the TSA policy OID, which is used to identify the time stamping policy. Additionally, time stamps contain the TSA digital certificate, which is needed to confirm the signature on the time-stamp. (Milinkovic, Milojkovic, Spasic & Lazic, 2013).

In their 2013 study, Milinkovic, Milojkovic, Spasic, and Lazic showed how they put a time-stamping authority (TMA) in place for government organizations. For all parties engaging in electronic commerce within the Republic of Serbia, the time stamps are issued by Serbia Post. After the setting was renamed, Linux workstations could use the Serbia POST-TMA, which had been developed for Windows machines. By using the Serbia TMA, users can effectively verify digital signatures even after the certificate that was used to establish the signature has expired, after it has been revoked, and by providing the precise time and date the document was signed.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

To understand how we can design a model to handle the smart transcript system for academic institutions of learning. The researchers harvested past work on digital signature and analysed them. To acquire relevant papers, Scopus, Google Scholar, and Web of Science were used as the three scientific databases searched. Alternative search strings were required due to user interface variations. Aware that this could lead to bias, the authors explored multiple keyword combinations, which resulted in a less inclusive sample. Below is a table showing the work, and the analysis made.

S/No	Title of Paper	Author(s) -	Year	Component Analysis
1	Trusted Academic Transcripts on the Blockchain: A Systematic Literature Review	Caldarelli, G., & Ellul, J.	2021	The implementation of blockchain technology for academic transcripts was the focus of this review. This review's findings emphasize the necessity for a uniform method based on a public blockchain to enable speedier adoption and acceptance. Additionally, oracles must be motivated through incentives, and their identities and activities must be recognized and identified for the system to be sustained.
2	Digital Certifications in Moroccan Universities: Concepts, Challenges, and Solutions	Litoussi et al	2022	Many Moroccan educational institutions are currently attempting to digitize their credentials. Digital certificates, such as an official academic transcript, registration certificate, or graduation, are secured using digital signatures provided by Barid eSign. For validity checks, all signed documents are kept on a centralized server. Finally, they suggested a decentralized digital certifications strategy based on blockchain.
3	Digital signatures: a tool to prevent and predict dishonesty?	Koning et al.	2020	Dishonesty is widespread and does significant harm to society. However, the digital revolution in society has resulted in changes in how people sign, which may impair the efficacy of this push. This study looked at the relationship between digital signatures in two experiments, expanding on prior research by looking at innovative signature kinds, the regulating influence of personal factors, effect decay, and the predicting value of digital signature attributes. The results reveal that no signature intervention has any effect and that there is no unilateral relationship between digital signature attributes and future behaviour. These findings contradict previous studies and call into question the utility of signature interventions to prevent or predict dishonest behaviour.
4	The Importance of Digital Signature in Sustainable Businesses: A Scale Development Study	Cavus & Sancar,	2023	To complete business transactions swiftly and reliably, digital signatures are required. 567 participants voluntarily participated in this study, which was designed as descriptive research. According to the statistical analysis

				<p>results, the produced scale has validity and reliability qualities and is qualified to be utilized in scientific study to measure people's consciousness of digital signatures. The digital signature scale, which is intended to cover a vacuum in the literature, is intended to assess people's familiarity with digital signatures in developing nations, particularly Cyprus, and to encourage them to use them after receiving the requisite training.</p>
5	<p>Gradubique: An Academic Transcript Database Using Blockchain Architecture</p>	<p>Thinh Nguyen</p>	<p>2018</p>	<p>Due to blockchain's fault tolerance and security characteristics, there is a growing desire among organizations for private solutions without cryptocurrency. Three blockchain architectures was investigated—Ethereum, Bitcoin and Hyperledger Fabric. Next, Gradubique, a blockchain that was built on Hyperledger Fabric, was created. Any school's instructors are able to upload exam and course grades to the Gradubique network via Gradubique. Gradubique offers transcript extraction for potential employers and graduate institutions. Through the use of blockchain technology, security is ensured.</p>
6	<p>AcaChain: Academic Credential Attestation System using Blockchain</p>	<p>Bhumichitr Channarukul</p>	<p>2020</p>	<p>Blockchain has piqued interest in a number of fields, including the development of digital currencies (such as Bitcoin), stocks, record-keeping, healthcare and much more. Blockchain technology has several important characteristics, including consensus, decentralization, distributed ledger, immutability, and smart contracts. This study investigates the potential applications of blockchain technology for the verification of academic credentials in the field of education. In order to save time, resources, and human participation, this article proposes to re-engineer the academic certification attestation process. In order to combat fake academic credentials, it also intends to build a special method for academic data collection. For the verification of academic credentials, a blockchain-based system has been put in place.</p>

7	TUDocChain- Securing Academic Certificate Digitally on Blockchain	Budhiraja Rani & 2019	Digital documents store the data in digital form while also authorizing the transfer of information. Academic Certificates give the go-ahead for the acquisition of learning outcomes. People need certificates for their professional pursuits. These certifications must be kept in readily accessible, tamper-proof ledgers for the foreseeable future. A certificate or learning certification should be saved since a blockchain archives transactions in a confirmable and persistent manner. Blockchain exposes certificate fraud and disassembles learning records. To do this, learning certificates' digital crypto-hashes are maintained, and authorisation integrity is controlled by creating smart contracts on the Blockchain. The TUDocChain is the platform that allows for the reliable and long-lasting authorization of academic diplomas on public ledgers.
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From the above research work analysed, six out of the seven articles reviewed, had the implementation of academic records, transcripts done using the blockchain technology. Blockchain technology as an emerging technology has actually seen a rise in implementation of use cases outside of the Cryptocurrency in which it was initially designed for.

Note that Blockchain uses cryptography to generate distinct wallet address for users. The cryptographic mechanism of the blockchain generate a private key (Known to the users only) and a public key that is for public consumption. Each transaction on the blockchain generates a cryptographic hash known as transaction hash. Similarly, Transmission of academic transcript can be sent and verified using digital signature model.

4.0 PROPOSED MODEL

To ensure a document's legitimacy, digital signatures are utilized. It employs two (asymmetric) keys that are mathematically tied to each other, making it so that a

communication encrypted using a private key can only be unlocked using the sender's public key. While a public key is visible to everyone, a private key is only known to the sender.

Our proposed system will perform two basic functions forward digitally signed transcripts; and authenticate these transcripts by verifying the signatures of the issuer. Each of these functions will have separate module to implement it.

Fig.1: The proposed secured model of transmitting transcripts

Fig.2: The proposed secured model of verifying transmitted transcripts

Addition of Blockchain to this method of transcript record request and verification can also enable transparency since the blockchain is usually a public ledger where all transactions can be verified on chain.

5.0 CONCLUSION

In this paper we analysed the current system of transcript processing in higher institution and related works academic records, digital signature and time-stamping. We designed a model a secured system for transmitting and verifying electronic transcripts using digital signature. Our proposed model will ensure that the electronic transcripts are not tampered with while in transit before reaching the intended recipient. We recommend the integration of time-stamping authority (TMA) in further studies.

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